

An Empirical Agent-Based Model for Twin Transition: Exploring regional pathways in Europe

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The twin transition, encompassing both digital and green transition, is a key challenge for Europe. In this study, we shift attention to the twin transition of technological knowledge bases of European regions. We employ an empirically grounded agent-based model (ABM) that allows to simulate technological knowledge creation – as captured by patents – of innovative agents in green and digital domains. Aggregated to the regional level, we use the model output to explore how local micro-level knowledge creation dynamics shape the regional twin transition progress. The twin transition trajectories are then further analysed through the lens of regional path development, meaning that the type of paths regions follow in the process of greening and digitalizing their knowledge bases are identified.

1. Introduction

The concept of twin transition is a cornerstone of European Union's strategy not only to address the climate crisis, but increasingly also to enhance Europe's global competitiveness (European Commission, 2020). It is based on the idea that synergies between digital and green transitions can accelerate the shift toward a greener economy, addressing environmental challenges, but also creating substantial economic opportunities in the mid- and long-run.

It is widely recognized that European regions vary significantly in their innovation capacities, institutional frameworks, industry structures, and technological capabilities – factors that critically shape their capacity to navigate and leverage the twin transition (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2023). In this context, this study aims to get a deeper understanding on how the twin transition unfolds in European regions, focusing on the transition of regional technological knowledge bases as one important precondition for its realisation. The underlying idea is that a shift towards green and digital technological knowledge bases, and in particular combinations thereof, constitutes an essential foundation for a region's ability to enter new industries, or adopt green or digital technologies in industrial production processes and practices (Damioli et al., 2024). Given the heterogeneity of regions, the exact technological trajectories they follow when greening and digitalising their knowledge bases can be diverse.

This study employs an empirically grounded agent-based model (ABM) on regional knowledge creation, further developing the model as introduced by (Neuländtner, 2020). While ABMs hold significant potential for testing STI indicators in real-world policy settings, they remain underutilized in empirical STI research. In this study, the regional twin transition is conceptualised as a bottom-up process, driven by knowledge creation activities of local agents. The behaviour of agents is shaped both by agent-specific characteristics and their regional environment. This reflects the idea that, although transitions may emerge as micro-level processes, they are highly influenced by broader factors, such as the regional innovation system (see e.g., Asheim et al., 2016; Rohe & Mattes, 2022). The objective of the study is twofold. First, it assesses how advanced European regions are in their twin transition, here defined as the number of green and digital specialisation each region has. Second, considering the

transition of the knowledge base as movement along technological trajectories, the study identifies the underlying paths driving green and digital transitions for each region.

To explore the heterogeneous underlying mechanisms by which regions undergo digital and green transition, the study takes the literature on new industrial path development as the conceptual starting point (see e.g. Asheim et al., 2016; Martin & Sunley, 2006). Central to this literature is the idea that regions follow diverse paths of development which are evolutionarily shaped by inherited industrial structures, existing local capabilities, the institutional environment, but also external influences (Tripl et al., 2018). This study distinguishes between four different development paths defined in the literature: *related diversification*, where a region diversifies into fields related to existing knowledge; *unrelated diversification*, where a region branches into unrelated fields; *path upgrade*, where a region moves into fields with higher value; and *importation*, where a region moves into entirely new activities (Grillitsch et al., 2018).

The study contributes to the existing literature in several ways. The ABM approach allows for a more dynamic analysis of twin transition capacities across European regions. Unlike retrospective empirical studies that rely on historical data (Jäger et al., 2025), this approach allows to identify regions that already can build on a technology portfolio that makes them likely candidates for a twin transition, even if they have not yet leveraged those capacities before. Further, based on regions' existing technology portfolios, we can identify which pathways lead to twin transition in different regions.

2. Methodology

Methodologically, this study adopts an empirical agent-based model (ABM) on regional knowledge creation (see Neuländtner, 2020) for the case of regional twin transition. The ABM stitches the micro-level and macro-level perspective together, allowing to analyse how the twin transition – defined as greening and digitalising the regional knowledge base – happens through agents' knowledge creation in green and digital and other (i.e., non-green and non-digital) technologies. In what follows, we initially describe the model conception in some more detail, and then discuss the model's output assessment in terms of a region's twin transition status and the underlying transition pathways.

2.1. Model conception

The basic conceptual foundation of the empirical ABM for regional twin transition grounds in the literature on regional innovation systems, where regional technological knowledge creation is driven by innovating organisations (agents) and their interactions. Accordingly, at the model's core are 70.000 empirically calibrated heterogeneous agents, representative of innovative *firms*, that may engage in a knowledge creation process (see Figure 1). The agents are located in 292 European NUTS2 regions. The main agent-level variables are (i) knowledge endowment, which is indicative of the technology classes (TCs) an agent has knowledge in, (ii) employee size and (iii) R&D intensity.

The agents' knowledge endowment is proxied by regional patent data, with TCs being represented by 735 3-digit level IPC and CPC classes (e.g., A61K), among which 92 are digital and 48 are green. For identifying green patent classes, the ENVTECH classification of the OECD is used (Hašič & Migotto, 2015). Also, all Y02 patents are classified as green. For digital patent classes we rely on the ICT classification of the OECD and the AI classification of WIPO. Data on variables (ii) and (iii) are based on region-level data from the Eurostat Structural Business Statistics. All empirical data is obtained for the years 2015-2017. Agents

are initialised using spatial microsimulation (see Neuländtner, 2020), meaning that the agent population of each region is sampled to be representative of empirical region-level data.

Figure 1: The agent’s knowledge creation process.

The knowledge creation process that agents undergo is illustrated in Figure 1. The objective of the agent in the simulation is to create new technological knowledge which can ultimately turn into a patent. At the beginning of the simulation, the agent decides based on a region-specific innovation probability – reflected by the share of innovative firms in the agent’s region (Eurostat Structural Business Statistics) – whether to engage in a knowledge creation process or not. The agent then chooses a starting technology class from its knowledge endowment and selects a research target – a technology class it aims to develop – and defines a research path, a sequence of technology classes leading to that target. The concept of technology space (see Neuländtner, 2020, among others) guides these choices, implying that an agent is more likely to choose a target TC proximate to the starting TC¹. The research path is set as the shortest weighted connection between starting TC and research target in technology space.

After choosing a research target, the agent decides between internal research and collaboration with other agents. The decision on whether or not to collaborate is based on an externally set collaboration parameter that is the same for all agents. The decision on the collaboration partner is based on a regional collaboration probabilities as obtained in a Spatial Interaction Model (SIM)², such as the region’s share of region-internal as compared to region-external research. Further, cognitive proximity, i.e., at least one overlapping TC in the knowledge endowment, is a requirement for collaboration.

The agent then starts the learning process, moving from TC to TC on the previously defined research path until the research target is reached. To determine whether a round of knowledge creation was successful, i.e., whether the agent moves to the next TC, research success is evaluated in each simulation step. For internal research, the success probability depends on the agent-specific characteristics defined above, namely overall technological expertise (defined as number of TCs an agent has knowledge in) and the R&D intensity of the agent, but also on the technological proximity between the involved technology classes. For collaborative research, success probability is calculated similarly to internal research but differs in that the R&D intensity and the overall expertise of the agent of the collaboration partnership that is highest is used to calculate the probability. This results in a higher likelihood of successful research when collaborating. In case of unsuccessful research, the agent will try again until research is successful. Successfully completing the research path, i.e., reaching the research target, results in a knowledge gain in all TCs on the research path.

2.1. Model outputs and their assessment

The knowledge gained in the learning process, can ultimately be translated into a patent, depending on an empirically grounded, region-specific patent propensity. The latter is estimated based on the obtained probabilities from a Poisson regression model, where key characteristics influencing patenting activity such as human resources, GRP per capita, R&D per capita, degree centrality are regressed on regional patent output³. This patent filter reflects the fact that certain

¹ In the model this is implemented with a decaying probability function, based on the technological distance between the classes in the technology space. That means that the probability of being chosen as a target TC shrinks with increasing distance to the agent’s starting TC.

² In the Spatial Interaction Model (SIM), the number of collaborations in EU framework projects (see risis2.eu for details) for each pair of regions are regressed on variables indicating (i) whether the regions share a border, (ii) the countries the regions are located in share a border, (iv) the regions belong to the same country and (v) the distance between the regions. Based on the model, collaboration probabilities are obtained for each pair of regions.

³ Data on GRP per capita, R&D per capita and human resources is obtained from Eurostat. Human resources are defined as number of persons with tertiary education (ISCED) and/or employed in science and technology. To account for the volatility of patent counts, we use averaged data from 2015–2017 for both patents and explanatory variables.

regions offer an environment that is more conducive to innovation. In this study, the model is simulated for 36 simulation steps, which we divide in three periods of 12 steps each. The number of patents agents produced in a certain TC, is then aggregated to the regional level. Regional patents developed in green and digital technology classes represents the main output dimension of interest in the context of our twin transition focus.

To evaluate how advanced a region is in terms of the green and digital transition of its knowledge base, the number of green and digital specialisations serves as a proxy. It is calculated based on the simulated green and digital patent output of the region. The concept of revealed technological advantage (RTA) is used to capture these specialisations. By definition of the RTA, region i has a specialisation in technology k if the share of technology k in the region's patent portfolio is higher than the share of technology k in the patent portfolio aggregated over the whole sample of n regions.

A region is considered advanced in the green (or digital) transition if the number of green (or digital) specialisations it achieves in the simulation falls within the top 25% of the empirical distribution of green (or digital) specialisations across the regions in our sample (based on patent data for the period of 2015-2017). Conversely, lagging regions are defined as those that fall below the median number of specialisations. Due to the stochastic nature of the model, the simulation is repeated 20 times to ensure robustness of the results. Only if the region reaches an advanced (lagging) transition status in at least 80% of the simulation runs, it is classified as advanced (lagging). This ensures that persistent over- or underperformance, rather than random variation, determines the twin transition status.

Given the varying preconditions of European regions for achieving twin transition (Fazio et al. 2024), the green and digital diversification processes that underpin these transitions may emerge from entirely different underlying dynamics, implying diverse types of twin transition paths (Trippel et al. 2020). Against this background, the study distinguishes four types of paths discussed in the literature on regional path development: *related diversification*, *unrelated diversification*, *importation*, and *path upgrade* as forms of new path development, and uses them as a framework to analyse which paths regions follow in their advances to twin transition. We introduce a taxonomy to determine for each green (digital) technology class in which a region has produced a patent in the ABM simulation, to which of the four path types it corresponds to. The pathway with the highest share, i.e., the pathway that occurs the most often in the regional green (digital) patent portfolio, represents the dominant pathway.

Table 1 provides an overview on how the pathways are operationalised. The pathways of *related diversification* and *unrelated diversification* solely depend on the dimension of relatedness, that means, on how related (proximate in the technology space) a green (digital) technology class, in which regional agents generated knowledge in, is to the existing regional technological knowledge base. To capture relatedness for each green (digital) technology in each region, the concept of relatedness density is employed (see e.g., Boschma et al., 2015). A technology classifies as *path upgrade* if the technology an agent diversifies into is complex, using the concept of knowledge complexity of regional knowledge bases (Pintar and Scherngell (2022)). Here, we calculate a measure that reflects the complexity level for each technology class, where high complex technologies can be understood as technologies that have low ubiquity and are at the same time produced in regions that are active in a broad variety of technologies. For *importation* both the dimensions of novelty and relatedness are relevant, meaning that a technology classifies for the pathway of importation if it is totally new to the region and at the same time not related to existing regional specialisations.

Table 1. Relevant dimensions for types of pathways.

Pathways	Relevant dimensions	Operationalisation
<i>Related diversification</i>	Green (digital) technologies are related to existing regional specialisations.	<i>if Relatedness density_{ik} > Q₇₅(Relatedness density)</i>
<i>Unrelated diversification</i>	Green (digital) technologies are unrelated to existing regional specialisations.	<i>if Relatedness density_{ik} < Q₅₀(Relatedness density)</i>
<i>Path upgrade</i>	Green (digital) technologies are complex according to our complexity measure.	<i>if technology k is complex</i>
<i>Importation</i>	Green (digital) technologies are not related to existing regional specialisations, and they are new to the region's patent portfolio.	<i>if Relatedness density_{ik} < Q₇₅(Relatedness density) ∧ technology k is novel</i>

Since the identification of the path type is done at the region-technology level, multiple green (digital) paths may be present in regions which are active in various green (digital) technologies. To identify the dominant green and digital path of a region, the identified paths are weighted by the technology's importance, i.e. the share of technology k share in the patent portfolio of region i .⁴ The green (digital) pathway with the highest share represents the dominant pathway.

3. Findings

In what follows, we present some initial results. We shift attention on two major aspects: *First*, the overall progress of a region towards green, digital or twin transition Figure 2(Figure 2), and *second*, an analysis on which pathway regions are moving in terms of their green (Figure 3) and digital (Figure 4) transition.

Concerning the overall status of transition (Figure 2), it can be seen that regions that are most advanced are located in Germany, Italy, the South of France, and the South of Scandinavia. We find spatial clusters of regions that are advanced in their green and digital transition. Irish and some Italian regions often reach an advanced digital transition state, while Northern German, Danish and Dutch region are often advanced in their green transition. Some other regions – particularly Eastern and South-Eastern European regions – do not substantially advance towards twin transition in the simulation. Comparing the first and the third simulation period, we see that many regions starting with an advanced green or digital transition state also achieve an advanced twin transition state in later periods, overall, a first indication that advancing digital and green knowledge bases indeed increase the likelihood for twin transition (see Bürscher et al., 2024).

⁴ Put formally, for each of the four path types, the following calculation is done: *Weighted path type* = $\sum_k Path\ type_{ik} * \frac{X_{ik}}{\sum_k X_{ik}}$, where X_{ik} refers to the number of patents region i has in green (digital) technology k in the analysed simulation period. The binary variable $Path\ type_{ik}$, reflecting whether a technology k in region i corresponds to the respective path type, is weighted by the share of green (digital) technology k in the total green (digital) patent portfolio of region i in the analysed simulation period.

Figure 2: Regions advanced in their green, digital and twin transition state in the first (left) and third (right) simulation period.

When looking at underlying pathways regions follow towards their green transition (Figure 3 left), we find that most advanced regions follow the pathway of related diversification. This means that the domains in which local actors generate new green knowledge, are closely connected to the region's existing strengths. In other words, it is the regions that can draw from a knowledge base related to green technologies that are most advanced in the green transition process. Exceptions are Stockholm, Upper Bavaria, Northwestern Switzerland and South Sweden which are on the pathway of unrelated diversification and still advanced in their green transition. This may be related to more mission-oriented R&D policy programmes, encouraging innovating actors to take higher risks in their research paths.

The map on the right side of Figure 3 shows path types of regions on the other end of the spectrum, namely those that are most lagging in the green transition process. We see that the pathways that the lagging regions follow are diverse. Some of them, e.g., Carinthia, Groningen or Saarland are on the pathway of related diversification, indicating that the green technologies they produce knowledge in are actually related to the local knowledge stock. In other words, this implies that these regions could principally draw on existing capabilities that enable green diversification (Grashof & Basilico, 2024; Orsatti et al., 2023), but these potentials are not yet realized, e.g. due to a lack of other resources. Many of them follow the pathway of importation (e.g., Murcia in Spain, Åland in Finland or Central and Southeastern Romania) or unrelated diversification (like Vienna, Budapest or Bucharest).

We find similar results for the digital transition paths of regions that are advanced in their digital transition (see Figure 4, left). While there is also a dominance of related diversification among regions advanced in terms of the digital transition of their knowledge base, there is, a higher variety of pathways. There are 13 regions (e.g., North Holland or Stockholm) that follow the pathway of upgrade and three regions on the pathway of unrelated diversification (Emilia-Romagna, Piemonte and Lombardia).

Figure 3: Green transition pathways in advanced (left) and lagging (right) regions.

For regions that are lagging in their digital transition, the most common pathway is unrelated diversification. This means that the digital technologies they produce tend to be unrelated to existing local specialisations. It is particularly Eastern European regions, but also regions in the Northern UK and Central France that remain lagging.

Figure 4: Digital transition pathways in advanced (left) and lagging (right) regions.

3. Conclusion

This study contributes to the growing body of research on twin transitions, employing an empirical Agent-based model (ABM) to evaluate the potentials and pathways of European regions for developing knowledge in green and digital technologies. By modelling regional twin transition (i.e., the rise of green and digital regional knowledge structures) as a result of knowledge creation activities of individual agents, the approach reflects the emergent nature of transitions. At the same time, the micro-level process of agents' knowledge creation is influenced by regional characteristics, acknowledging the role of the broader regional environment in enabling or constraining the agents' capacity to generate new knowledge and, ultimately, drive transitions.

Our findings highlight distinct pathways between regions that are advanced in their twin transition and those that are lagging. Regions at the forefront of green or digital transition tend to follow a path of related diversification. These regions green and digitalise their knowledge bases, by building on established local capabilities. This reflects a strategic leveraging of existing strengths and is in line with the principle of relatedness (Hidalgo et al., 2018), which suggests that regions with existing technological capabilities that are closely related to green (or digital) domains are more likely to successfully undergo a green (or digital) transition.

In contrast, lagging regions often follow more diverse pathways. Rather than relying on related diversification, they are more likely to green and digitalise their knowledge base along the pathway of unrelated diversification or importation. In other words, the green and digital technologies in which lagging regions begin to develop knowledge in, tend to be either entirely new to the region, corresponding to the pathway of importation, or only weakly connected to the existing local knowledge base, representing unrelated diversification. These findings support the theoretical perspective of Grillitsch and Hansen (2019), who argue that in peripheral regions with weak or thin innovation systems, *related diversification* is often not a relevant strategy of new path development, as it requires accumulated knowledge and resources from one industrial specialisation in another industry and that, instead, such regions may need to rely on *importation*, drawing on external knowledge and resources to initiate new development pathways.

These initial findings point to potential policy implications, suggesting that efforts to foster green and digital transitions must account for the varying capacities of regions to leverage their existing knowledge bases. This means that, while encouraging regions to transition toward greener and more digital knowledge structures, policies should support regions to build on existing local capabilities where possible and facilitate knowledge inflows—such as through cross-regional collaboration—where internal capacities are limited. Future model applications will allow for the implementation of policy scenarios and will bring more systematic evidence on the impact of policy intervention on both the twin transition progress of regions and the pathways regions are moving along.

Open science practices

The initialisation of the agent, such as the analysis of the model output was done in R. The source code is available upon request. All data are openly available and were obtained from OECD's REGPAT database, Eurostat and EUPRO.

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Author contributions

Theresa Bürscher: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing, Visualisation; **Katharina Jäger:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Writing; **Martina Neuländtner:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Writing; **Thomas Scherngell:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Writing, Supervision.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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